

VICE4RAIL
EGNSS - ERTMS

VICE4RAIL

GNSS AUTOMATED VIRTUALIZED TEST ENVIRONMENT
FOR RAIL

FOREWORD

EGNSS (European Global Navigation Satellite System) is one of the game-changing technologies for the evolution of the European Rail Traffic Management System (ERTMS). Its integration into the ERTMS can improve safe train localization and offer considerable benefits to the entire sector. However, the implementation of this technology faces challenges due to the lack of a standardized and industry-accepted certification methodology specifically designed to meet the unique requirements of the railway industry. The VICE4RAIL project aims to address this gap by exploring suitable certification procedures that comply with ERTMS standards and CENELEC norms applicable to EGNSS technology, thereby contributing to the development of a future certification process for its integration into the ERTMS framework. To this scope the VICE4RAIL project is developing a Hybrid Virtualized Testing Certification Environment, HyVICE, tailored to EGNSS-based localization solutions for the ERTMS. This hybrid testing environment is indispensable to assess rare faults of EGNSS signals that are almost impossible to verify with field tests. It combines laboratory simulations and realistic on-field testing to certify the EGNSS-based train positioning systems. By replicating real-world operational conditions in a controlled environment, HyVICE will ensure a cost-effective, repeatable, and comprehensive approach to the assessment and certification of train localization technologies.

This 1st Newsletter provides an insight of the main outcomes and achievements of the activities related to WP2. These activities mainly encompass gathering and defining the user and system requirements specific to rail applications, as well as designing a comprehensive certification plan for the VICE4RAIL solution. In addition, they explore how lessons learned and established practices from the automotive and maritime sectors can be leveraged to create synergies in the certification process, ultimately fostering more robust and efficient procedures across industries. Next newsletter will provide an insight of the first WP3 results.

PROJECT STRUCTURE

VICE4RAIL aims to promote the adoption of EGNSS for implementing efficient, resilient, and competitive ERTMS systems. VICE4RAIL high-level objectives are:

- Contribute to the development of a standardized certification methodology aimed at creating a harmonized European framework for certifying satellite-based train positioning systems. This will ensure reliability, compliance with safety standards, and adherence to regulatory requirements.
- Develop the HyVICE testing environment that combines real-world and simulated testing to form a comprehensive and versatile evaluation platform for satellite positioning technologies in various railway operations scenarios.
- Support the future TSI potentially integrating High Accuracy and High Integrity GNSS technology into the ERTMS standard. This will help to close the certification gaps and enable early adoption of GNSS-based systems across Europe.

To achieve the aforementioned high-level objectives, the proposed activities are organized into six distinct Work packages, as depicted in the Figure 1 below.

Figure 1: The VICE4RAIL work breakdown structure

WP1 and WP6 are non-technical work packages responsible for project monitoring and control (WP1) and project dissemination, communication, and exploitation activities (WP6). WP2 focuses on specifying requirements and developing an industry-accepted certification plan for architecture validation in WP5. WP3 involves designing the System Requirements, the overall and detailed architecture as well as the relevant Test Plan for both the Laboratory and the On-field/Mixed Reality Testing Platforms. WP4 is dedicated to the development, integration, and testing of each subsystem of HyVICE platform. The results from both laboratory and field tests are used in WP5 to perform the final validation of the HyVICE Platform. In WP5, a NoBo participates according to its accredited role to simulate a certification process, evaluating the conformity of the Essential Requirements and Technical Compatibility for the trackside and on-board system.

Hybrid Virtualized Testing Certification Environment Requirements / Development of certification plan (WP2)

WP2 focuses on the specification of requirements and the development of an industry-accepted risk assessment and certification plan for HyVICE architecture validation within WP5. In more details, WP2 consists of the following objectives:

- Specification of rail user, functional, system safety and security requirements for the HyVICE – to establish a clear understanding of system needs and constraints. Application of a so-called Common Safety Method for Risk evaluation and Assessment (CSM-RA) according to the Regulation (EU) 402/2013 – for mandatory risk management process related to HyVICE,
- Development of the industry-accepted plan for the HyVICE certification, to guide the implementation of validation and certification in line with industry standards, and finally,
- Investigation and exploitation of synergy effects in rail, automotive and maritime GNSS-based safety applications – to find efficient certification solutions in multimodal transport.

Results from previous / ongoing projects such as HELMET, ERSAT GGC, GATE4RAIL, STARS, STEMS, CLUG, X2RAIL-2, X2RAIL-5, and R2DATO were used as inputs to WP2. To address the above-mentioned objectives, the following tasks were specified within WP2:

- T2.1: Rail user & system requirements (led by RFI) - *Duration: M1-M6*,
- T2.2: Development of the certification plan for the VICE4RAIL solution (led by Italcertifier) - *Duration: M1-M10*,
- T2.3: Synergies between rail, automotive and maritime in the certification process (led by University of Pardubice) - *Duration: M1-M10*.

All tasks were completed by the end of July 2025 and the results are summarized in the four public deliverables below:

- D2.1: Rail user & system requirements (led by RFI),
- D2.2: Risk analysis evaluation report (led by Italcertifier),
- D2.3: Certification plan (led by Bureau Veritas), and
- D2.4: Synergies in the certification process for use in multimodal transport (led by University of Pardubice).

The main results of WP2 can be summarized as follows:

D2.1: Rail user & system requirements: This document is related to task T2.1 and defines the rail user and system requirements that will guide the development of the project's hybrid virtualized testing and certification framework. The methodology leverages outcomes from previous and ongoing EU initiatives, particularly the Europe's Rail Joint Undertaking Flagship Project 2 (FP2) R2DATO. VICE4RAIL directly supports Europe's Rail, aligning with the Advanced Safe Train Positioning (ASTP) vision, expected to be incorporated into future Technical Specifications for Interoperability (TSIs).

An overview of European railway regulations and standards, user needs, functional and non-functional system requirements, and preliminary requirements for a virtual certification platform called HyVICE are provided. The aim is to create a reliable and efficient framework that facilitates the certification of EGNSS-based solutions by adhering to the highest safety and interoperability standards. The HyVICE platform is envisaged as a comprehensive environment combining laboratory simulations and realistic on-field testing to certify GNSS-based train positioning systems.

D2.2: Risk analysis evaluation report: Since the introduction of GNSS into ERTMS/ETCS represents an important novelty and also the potential excessive safety risk associated with this change within the European railway network, then the Common Safety Method for Risk Evaluation and Assessment (CSM-RA) must be applied under Regulation (EU) 402/2013 in order to manage the safety risk to the acceptable level see Figure 2.

The delivered document “Risk Analysis Evaluation Report” is a summary of work carried out within task T2.2 and its purpose is to assess the compliance of the preliminary hazard analysis conducted within the project with the CSM-RA framework. The process in terms of CSM-RA was collectively developed by the entire VICE4RAIL consortium and the final goal is to contribute to the introduction of standardized EGNSS-based localization solutions to be used within the European Rail Traffic Management System (ERTMS). In deliverable D2.2, the application of CSM-RA within the research project was evaluated by the Inspection Organization. D2.2 consists of sections such as Description of the change, Independent risk assessment plan, Analysis of impact and significance for safety, Evaluation of the risk management process and Conclusions.

Figure 2: Railway safety standards, interoperability and common safety method

D2.3: Certification plan: This document is one of the outputs of task T2.2 which defines the guidelines and the roadmap for the verification and validation process of the HyVICE test platform. This process will be adopted for the future certification of GNSS-based train positioning solutions for ERTMS/ETCS applications, with the aim of contributing to the achievement of the following objectives:

1. To contribute to the establishment of a standardized methodology for the future certification of GNSS-based train localization solutions (e.g. ASTP) and to develop a harmonized European framework to ensure reliability, compliance and regulatory alignment;
2. to construct a dedicated reference dynamic test environment (i.e. the HyVICE test platform) based on the 'near zero-on-site' testing approach, to support the future assessment and certification process for GNSS-based train localization solutions (e.g. ASTP);
3. to provide guidelines for the preliminary verification of the compliance of the HyVICE test platform with the relevant technical requirements defined in the Regulatory Standards, to be used by Notified Bodies (NoBo) and Assessment Bodies (AsBo) as a starting point for the future certification of GNSS-based train localization solutions (e.g. ASTP);

- to proceed to quantify and model the effects of the electromagnetic environment on GNSS and IMU technologies included in the HyVICE validation and testing simulation environment.

D2.4: Synergies in the certification process for use in multimodal transport: This document, as an output of task T2.3, describes an overview of safety assessment and certification procedures in the rail, automotive and maritime sectors with the aim of identifying common elements to streamline the certification of GNSS-based positioning in multimodal transport – see Figure 3.

D2.4 demonstrates the practical application of the analysed synergies in the certification process using the example of the identified common element, which is GNSS continuity. It is shown what role GNSS continuity plays in achieving the required reliability or safety of positioning in land transport. It should be noted that the use of GNSS continuity has not been sufficiently explored in recent R&D projects on GNSS safety applications in rail or road transport – even though GNSS continuity in aviation has significant impact on the cost of GNSS infrastructure.

Although the presented outputs are the result of a comparative analysis related to safe GNSS based positioning in different transport sectors, they will mainly guide the project's development of a hybrid virtualized testing and certification framework tailored specifically for EGNSS-based train positioning solutions. Nevertheless, the synergies described in D2.4 can also be used for the safety assessment and certification of GNSS safety applications in other modes of transport.

One of the main findings obtained using Markov modelling is the improvement of the reliability of GNSS-based positioning systems in terms of the Mean Time to System Failure (MTTF_{sys}). This can be significantly increased from approximately 521 hours, corresponding to the aviation continuity for a Category I approach, to 5x10⁵ hours required for GNSS-based positioning for ERTMS.

Figure 3: Methodology for exploiting synergies in the certification process of GNSS-based safety applications in multimodal transport

WCRR 2025

The VICE4RAIL project team is proud to announce an early start of the dissemination task with three papers that have been officially accepted for presentation at the World Congress of Rail Research (WCRR) 2025 - the world's largest international congress on railway research. This edition is set to take place in Colorado Springs, Colorado, USA, from November 17 to 21, 2025, stands as a beacon for the exchange of forward-thinking ideas and transformative solutions in the rail industry.

Under the theme, "Inspiring Innovative and Resilient Railways," WCRR 2025 will gather leading rail professionals, policy-makers, and visionary industry representatives from across the globe. The congress promises to be a dynamic forum dedicated to sharing knowledge, fostering international collaboration, and highlighting the latest advancements in railway technology and research.

The papers deal with the main topic of the VICE4RAIL project offering an opportunity to share with the international railways community its vision and the expected results:

"Transforming Rail Safety and Efficiency: A Certification Methodology for GNSS Integration into ERTMS Using a Hybrid Virtualized Testing Environment"

"Certification approach for innovative product and system development. How to manage third part evaluation for innovative technologies in railway signaling in a framework of interoperability"

"The Role of Continuity Attribute for Train Positioning Technologies Based on GNSS and ERTMS"

The acceptance of these papers underscores the VICE4RAIL project commitment to advancing the hybrid cutting-edge testing solutions and sustainable methodologies for accelerating the certification process of the GNSS technologies in the frame of the ERTMS ecosystem. WCRR 2025 represents an opportunity to rise the importance on the benefits brought by the GNSS technologies once the certification methodologies have been agreed and can be implemented with an efficient process.

TOTAL PROJECT
VALUE
2.7 M

PARTNERS
9

DURATION
36
Months

PROJECT PARTNERS

CONTACT US

PROJECT COORDINATOR

Rete Ferroviaria Italiana (RFI) Piazza
della Croce Rossa 1
00161 Rome, Italy

PROJECT WEBSITE

www.vice4rail.eu

This project is funded by European Union's Horizon Europe
programme under grant agreement No 101180124

